

MICRO ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF FERROUS AND FERRIC IRON IN MINERALS.

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A micro-analytical method for the estimation of ferrous and ferric iron in the same sample of mineral has been proposed. The method consists in decomposing the mineral with a mixture of hydrochloric and hydrofluoric acid in a pyrex glass vessel and titrating the ferrous iron in the resulting solution with ceric sulphate and the total iron subsequently with titanous chloride. Two sets of redox indicators have been used namely, (i) ferrous *o*-phenanthroline complex with methylene blue and (ii) *N*-phenylanthranilic acid with potassium thiocyanate. The method has been successfully used for the micro-estimation of ferric and ferrous iron in minerals such as magnetite, ilmenite, etc.

Pichler first developed a method for the micro-estimation of ferrous iron with diphenylamine as internal indicator in which an addition of extra ferric chloride was needed for a sharp end-point, and the method gave a maximum relative error of 3% (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1928, 73, 209). Kolthoff and Server (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4190; 1931, 53, 2609) studied the properties of various redox indicators and reported better result with diphenylsulphonic acid. Ferrous *o*-phenanthroline complex has been worked out and has also been employed as an indicator for the micro-estimation of iron (Walden, Hammet and Chapman, *ibid.*, 1933, 55, 2649; Fryling and Tooley, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 826). An indicator correction was, however, found to be necessary by the latter workers. A correction for the silver reductor in which the iron solution was reduced was also found unavoidable.

Following Karsonov, Syrokomsy and Stiepin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 928) found *N*-phenylanthranilic acid a better substitute for ferrous *o*-phenanthroline complex as it requires no indicator correction.

A method for the purpose of estimating both the ferrous and ferric iron in one and the same solution and its adaptation to micro scale is described in the present paper using ceric sulphate and titanous chloride reagents with two sets of different redox indicators like (i) *o*-phenanthroline ferrous complex with methylene blue, and (ii) *N*-phenylanthranilic acid with potassium thiocyanate solution. No indicator correction is necessary. *N*-phenylanthranilic acid was used as an indicator for the estimation of ferrous iron and potassium thiocyanate when estimating the total iron. Boric acid was added before the titration as proposed by Barneyley (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 148) to remove the disturbing influence of the excess of hydrofluoric acid used to dissolve the mineral. Small quan-

tities of iron of the order of 10^{-2} mg. present in the mineral both in the ferrous and ferric state could be estimated by this method with good results.

E X P E R I M A N T A L I.

The mineral (20—50 mg.) was carefully weighed into a pyrex conical flask (100 c.c.) previously filled with pure carbon dioxide, which was purified by passing through two wash bottles containing (i) stannous chloride to remove any oxidising substances, and (ii) sodium bicarbonate to remove impurities like $\text{SO}_2, \text{H}_2\text{S}$. etc. After passing the gas for a few minutes hydrofluoric acid (1-2 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) were quickly introduced into the flask and it was heated on an electric heater to about 50° . The ore dissolved in a few minutes (it takes a longer time when the titanium content is high), the flask was cooled and the current of carbon dioxide increased. To the solution in the flask about 35 c.c. of 5% boric acid solution (in $N/2$ HCl) were added and the solution diluted with water (previously boiled to remove dissolved oxygen) so that the acid strength was about $2N$. One drop of ferrous *o*-phenanthroline ($0.025M$) was added as an internal indicator and the whole was titrated with standard ceric sulphate solution from a microburette. Before the titration a few drops (about 0.5 c.c.) of syrupy phosphoric acid was added to get a sharp end-point. When the end-point was reached 1 drop of methylene blue was added and the whole solution was again titrated with standard titanous chloride.

Sharp end-point with methylene blue could be obtained only at 35° . Addition of 1 or 2 drops of 10% sodium salicylate solution with methylene blue gives the same effect at lower temperatures.

After both the titrations were over and the proper indicator correction applied from blank experiments, the ferric iron present in the solution was calculated.

With ferrous *o*-phenanthroline and methylene blue a sample of magnetite gave the results shown in Table I A.

TABLE I.

A.			B.		
Ore taken.	Ferrous iron.	Total iron.	Ore taken.	Ferrous iron	Total iron.
0.03040 g.	22.4%	67.0%	0.02876 g.	22.35%	67.3%
0.2310	22.3	67.2	0.02279	22.3	67.2
			0.01950	22.2	67.1

Sample from the same magnetite was analysed as before but with phenylanthranilic acid and potassium thiocyanate as indicators. Without any indicator correction and without the addition of phosphoric acid the results shown in Table I B were obtained.

The magnetite, when analysed by the standard method using standard potassium dichromate solution and diphenylamine, was found to contain ferrous iron to the extent of 22.3% and total iron, 67.3%.

Indicator Correction.—With ceric sulphate and ferrous *o*-phenanthroline complex, when the standard titrating solution is sufficiently dilute, indicator correction is essential as evident from Table II.

TABLE II.

Ferrous <i>o</i> -phenanthroline (0.025 <i>M</i>) taken (c.c.)	...	0.01	0.02	0.028	0.03
Ceric sulphate required to discharge the colour (c.c.)	...	0.06	0.11	0.16	0.17

The indicator correction graph when plotted gives a straight line.

Table III shows that no indicator correction is necessary with *N*-phenylanthranilic acid. About 5 drops of the indicator (1.07 g. of the acid with 10 g. of sodium carbonate per litre) was found to give a sharp endpoint.

TABLE III.

<i>N</i> -Phenylanthranilic acid (c.c.)	...	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.30	0.35	0.40
Ceric sulphate soln. required for colour change (c.c.)	...	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01

No phosphoric acid was added in the above titrations.

Similarly with methylene blue and titanous chloride an indicator correction is essential as the dye is quantitatively reduced by the titanous chloride solution. Blank experiments demonstrate that these indicators used in combination exert no mutual effect upon one another. Different amounts of ferrous *o*-phenanthroline were taken and after the colour was discharged with ceric sulphate, one drop of methylene blue (1%) and two drops of sodium salicylate (10%) were added and the solution was again titrated with titanous chloride solution.

TABLE IV.

Ferrous <i>o</i> -phenanthroline added (c.c.) ...	0'012	0'02	0'03	0'04	0'06
Titanous chloride required for 1 drop of methylene blue (c.c.) ...	0'08	0'08	0'09	0'08	0'09

In all the above experiments about $N/100$ -ceric sulphate solution in dilute sulphuric acid was used. Titanous chloride when prepared in $2N$ -hydrochloric acid solution was found to be more stable.

The Micro Method.—Pure ferrous ammonium sulphate carefully weighed in a microbalance, was dissolved in $2N$ -hydrochloric acid, 0'05 c.c. of phosphoric acid (when ferrous *o*-phenanthroline was used as indicator) was added to obtain a sharp end-point. Hydrofluoric acid (1 c.c., 40%) and boric acid solution (35 c.c.) were introduced in to the flask. Hydrochloric acid was added to bring the solution to $2N$ and titrated first with ceric sulphate and then with titanous chloride using the two sets of redox indicators previously mentioned. The results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V.

Indicator: (i) Ferrous *o*-phenanthroline, and (ii) methylene blue.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate taken.	Fe calc.	Fe Found with	
		$\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$.	TiCl_3 .
4'541 mg.	0'6485 mg.	0'6462 mg.	0'6460 mg.
4'671	0'6685	0'6658	0'6658
4'469	0'6380	0'6470	0'6400
4'470	0'6380	0'6400	0'6390

(i) Phenylanthranilic acid (1'07 g. with 10 g. of Na_2CO_3 per litre), and (ii) potassium thiocyanate (10%).

4'124 mg.	0'589 mg.	0'600	0'592
3'827	0'546	0'553	0'546
7'678	1'096	1'092	1'092
4'173	0'596	0'614	0'621
3'343	0'474	0'477	0'481
2'735	0'391	0'396	0'390

In the above titrations no phosphoric acid was added. The results found are quite satisfactory.

In the case of a mineral the ore was crushed in an iron mortar and purer pieces were sorted out with the help of a pair of tongs. The small pieces were then purified with the help of a horse shoe magnet. They were again crushed and sieved by a 150-mesh sieve. The powdered ore was then further purified by magnetic separation. Micro quantities of the ore (as well as semimicro and macro quantities) were weighed out in a 100 c.c. pyrex Erlenmeyer flask (Soule, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1691) filled with pure carbon dioxide as previously stated. Hydrofluoric acid (2-3 c.c.) and about 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added and the flask was heated in an electric heater. In the decomposition of the ore hydrochloric acid was found to be more convenient than sulphuric acid specially in the case of magnetite (*cf.* Adam, *J. South African Chem. Inst.*, 1925, 8). The ore decomposed in a few minutes, the solution was cooled down and the rate of carbon dioxide flow increased. Boric acid solution (35 c.c., 5% in *N/2*-hydrochloric acid solution) was added and the solution was kept about 2*N* (only boiled and cooled water was used when dilution was necessary). The solution was titrated in a current of carbon dioxide. Phenylanthranilic acid (5-6 drops of the solution) and potassium thiocyanate (10 c.c. of 5% solution) were used as indicator for which no indicator correction was required. The results are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

A. Magnetite.			B. Ilmenite.		
Amount taken.	Fe ⁺⁺ [by Ce(SO ₄) ₂].	Total Fe (by TiCl ₃).	Amount taken.	Fe ⁺⁺ iron [by Ce(SO ₄) ₂].	Total iron [by TiCl ₃].
3'310 mg.	22'6%	67'2%	1'207 mg	28'6%	43'37%
4'274	22'4	67'0	2'791	28'2	43'55
3'165	22'6	67'1	2'666	28'2	43'60
1'884	22'5	67'3	3'781	28'4	43'20
Mean	22'5	67'2	Mean	{28'35	43'43
	22'3*	67'0		28'40*	*43'5
				28.45†	†43'5

* By Macro method.

† By Semi-micro method.

Ilmenite.

The same procedure was adopted in the analysis of ilmenite. Longer time was required in the decomposition of the mineral probably due to the higher titanium content.

The method can thus be conveniently used for the micro estimation of ferrous and ferric iron present in the same mineral sample.

Restriction—The method is applicable only when the interfering substances like trivalent vanadium etc. are absent.

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